

Product Features based Sentiment Analysis from Twitter

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Abstract— People’s opinions are considered as the most powerful source of market research. Popularly, Social Media has become a tool that is used in an easy way including huge number of users who can share their opinions about products or services and their thoughts about current problems of the society and express their views on political and religious issues. The knowledge extracted from social media contains sentiment data – that is not included in corporate database – that can be used to improve the marketing campaigns to retain customers and meet their needs in a better way. The integration and merging between both social media data and corporate data can lead to better insights that would not have been possible to gain without such integration. In this paper, we will use Twitter as a social media source platform to do a feature based level sentiment analysis using tweets including opinions about a specific product. . The research discussed three different ways to extract (feature/opinion) pairs from each text including: Normal Tokenization, N-gram Modeling Extraction, and Noun Chunking Extraction. The extracted opinion phrase related to each extracted feature is being classified using sentiment classification algorithm. A decision is taken about the best between the three ways according to the resulted measurements. SCDJF had been evaluated using multiple techniques. The best results occurred from Noun Chunking Extraction with accuracy 77%. Summarization of the results will show how this can be used to enhance decision making process of the organization. Summarization of the results will show how this can be used to enhance decision making process of the organization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Business Intelligence and Analytics are considered as being the processes of extracting and predicting critical insights from different available types of data that are important to the business. The user-generated content considered to be the major component of social media that defines the characteristics of Web 2.0. To develop information connections, individuals are using variety of technologies to access content and join virtual communities on various social networking sites. Most of researchers and organizations are interested in the individuals' perception of social networking sites taking into consideration the dimensions of ease-of-use, usefulness, feeling, usage intention, and information quality. With the rise of this type of big data, there are a lot of opportunities and challenges for the business intelligence especially with the growing number of data sources.

Collecting social media data is considered to be the basis of the analysis process as it has become a necessity for most companies to monitor social media reviews about their products and services. In order to do so, companies started to

manually reviewing mentions of their brands on different social media platform. The manual approach proved to be not scalable with the huge amount of reviews and does not enable companies to detect real-time customers’ insights not to engage with social customers in a relevant and timely manner. Moreover, in order for companies to gain insights from both social media and their corporate data, data practices need to be adapted and extended to join both types of data. This new joined database can be easily accessed by business intelligence tools for querying and visualization.

Because organizations spent a lot of money and time on surveying their products to get customers' feedback so they can know the defects of the system for the future enhancements. As a result, there has been a tremendous need to design methods and algorithms which can effectively process wide variety of text applications. Given a dataset of texts containing opinions about a specific product as a target to extract useful opinions about product features with polarity definition of each opinion and represent them in a format that is easy to digest. This thesis’s objective is to study doing sentiment analysis on the feature level after extracting every product feature from each opinion text; which may contain more than one feature with the related opinion word; by defining the polarity of opinions; which can be negative or positive; attached with each feature separately which resulted in that each text may contain more than one sentiment and they may be contradicting with each other. Having a collection of opined texts about a specific product, the main aim is to extract the features stated in each text with the opinion word that described each feature, filtering the feature-opinion pairs based on the frequency of each feature and then identify the associated sentiments with joining the resulted structured data with corporate database and display a summary of obtained results. The product features were identified in this thesis as explicitly mentioned features that appear as nouns or noun phrases in the opinion text. Fig 1 shows the general architecture of the generated business intelligence framework.

Fig. 1. Research Objective in business intelligence framework

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents Social Business Intelligence background. Section 3 summarizes the related work. A discussion about the proposed framework with introducing a case study leveraging that framework is presented in section 4. An evaluation of the proposed framework presented in section 5 and we conclude in section 6.

II. BACKGROUND

Business Intelligence and Analytics are considered as being the processes of extracting and predicting useful insights from available data that is important to the business. Traditional business intelligence concentrated on collecting, extracting and organizing data with ability to make efficient query processing for insights deriving from historical structured data [18]. Business Intelligence applications can support decision makers by providing meaningful information from the data that is mainly comes from operational databases and structured data sources.

A. Business Intelligence

Business Intelligence described the process of turning raw data into knowledge used to make business decisions. Business Intelligence tasks are performed on data that is typically loaded into data warehouse and managed by one or more data warehouse services. Database management systems (RDBMSs) are used for storing and querying warehouse data by running queries. Fig 2 summarizes the key components of business intelligence [11].

Fig. 2. Typical Business Intelligence Architecture

B. Big Data

Big Data is considered to be the raw materials that the social media companies trade in. It contains information about the intent of millions of people. There are a lot of opportunities and challenges for the business intelligence especially with the growing number of data sources. Business Intelligence and analytics are evolving to provide intelligence at different perspectives and scales [18]. There is a direction to propose low-cost data platforms that can support much bigger data amounts than that handled by relational DBMS traditionally. Large applications are capable of translating massive amounts of data into information that can be read and interpreted by people and this is the knowledge that needs to be caught. The quality of big data is also considered to be non-trivial problem. Many statistical methods of data analysis relying on data sets collected randomly from sampled populations or the sampling bias needs to be incorporated into the statistical model in some way. This is difficult when dealing with Big Data because it is not clear whether the data is disfigured and how this happened. Big data is also frequently messy and containing errors and omissions as artifacts of the process of collecting data and sharing it. To address this, there is a need to clean most of Big Data before doing computational analysis to be consistent and to remove the errors in the data.

C. Social Media

Although social media platforms have widespread availability and stature as a driver of the global conversation thanks to be synonymous with big data, there is a lack of external visibility into those platforms means that almost all of organizations' assessments are based on the statistics that are hand-picked by those companies which reporting to the public and the trillion ways those figures, such as active users are constantly evolved to reflect the image possible of the growth of social media as a whole.

The content generated by users is the major component of social media that defines the characteristics of Web 2.0. So, Social media should include online communication, which means that the history of social media cannot begin before the widespread adoption and invention of the internet; and because of depending on user-generated content, typical blogs and websites do not get included in the world of social media.

With more concern, Social Network Sites contained Web-based services where individuals can construct dynamic public profiles about themselves that contain their various educational background, philosophies, interests, and demographic information and are shared with other individuals. Within the specific social networking site, individuals can allocate their relationship with other users and also viewing users who are following their sites. With such a huge amount of the available data, marketers have the ability to utilize it to get actionable insights for framing efficient strategies for social media marketing. All the photos, videos, and status updates that are posted by users on their social network contain useful information about their likes, dislikes, demographics, etc. Businesses are using this information in various different ways, analysing and managing it to get a competitive rim. Big data make the marketers able to identify social media trends and gain insights and that can be used to make engagement decisions like deciding on which users to communicate with, which group of users should receive the marketing emails, etc. It also enables keeping track of the

demographics easily to decide on targeted social media platform. Social media marketers can use big data to judge future buying patterns and trends in an effective way. Big data increases the accuracy regarding what consumers want, how they want it, and when they want it. This gives businesses insights to know how their new products should be like.

Opinion mining and sentiment analysis are used to automatically extract knowledge/ opinion from text represented by reviews/comments and/or statuses about a particular product or topic. Through these opinions, we can extract information about the product and analyse them to get sentiment analysis results. Organizations spent a lot of money and time on surveying their products to get customers' feedback. So, they can know the defects of the system for the future enhancements. As a result, there has been a tremendous need to design methods and algorithms which can effectively process wide variety of text applications [39].

Sentiment Analysis is all about extracting opinions from the text. There are various aspects, reasons, orientation of extracting these emotions according to the reason behind the analysis and this problem has been studied by many researchers in the past few years. Three different levels on which sentiment analysis can be performed depending upon the granularities required. Document level sentiment analysis using supervised or unsupervised machine learning approaches, Sentence level sentiment analysis counting on subjectivity classification or polarity classification and have level sentiment analysis supported Part-Of-Speech (POS) tagging.

III. RELATED WORK

Because of the unstructured nature of social data, there are a lot of challenges and difficulties to deal with that type of data, analysing them, and extracting valuable information from such data. A lot of research and literature reviews done to address challenges and difficulties involved in processing social media data using specific data analysis methods. However, there hardly exists research on the stages of data discovery, collection, and preparation as they are considered the most challenging phases in the analysis process. In 2018, researchers addressed this gap and conducted an extended and structured literature analysis through identifying challenges and proposing solutions [11]. From this point, researchers continued to get benefits of analysing social media that utilized to forecast future outcomes by studying creating sentiments, how positive and negative opinions propagate and how they influence people and be effective indicators of real-world performance [8].

To be able to apply sentiment analysis on extracted data from social media, there is a need to ensure that the extracted data contained opinions and emotions that can be analysed using sentiment analysis and polarity identification techniques. In 2012, researchers concentrated on finding opinionated tweets about a given topic by proposing a ranking model for opinion retrieval in Twitter that integrates social and opinionatedness information for tweets opinion retrieval taking into consideration mentions, links, author information such as the number of statues or followers and the opinionatedness of the tweet [2]. In 2013, researchers continued to find a solution to help agents find opinionated customers by introducing twitter based filtering system called

CrowdE that creates the filters through machine learning over crowd-labelled tweets [3].

After ensuring the subjectivity of the extracted social media data before sentiment analysis and classification, there is a need to detect these expressed opinions in such a way. Simply, [12] used two techniques, namely, supervised training represented by the probabilistic Bayesian model and semantic orientation represented by the algorithm of Turney. The first one is based on the emoticons, whereas the second is based on adjectives which are applied according to a predefined pattern and models of POS labels to extract expressions with two words from reviews. By referring to using adjectives as opinion phrases that are considered to be the input of the sentiment analysis process, there is a need to give attention at taking the negation into consideration when deciding the polarity of the opinion phrase. Our research shows that it is better not to depend only on emoticons to decide the sentiment of a sentence but it is a must to take the semantic orientation of words into consideration.

Researchers in [39] presented an algorithm to extract opinions from a micro-blogging site on which an organization trusts and consider its reviews with a try to create database of online opinions. The advantage in that research is that it is a foundation to define a structure to the extracted opinion. They summarized the opinion aspects as shown [10] in figure 3.2 and this makes it easy to define the fields of attributes that will be included in the created database. Our work is different as they did not continue to do sentiment analysis and classification on the extracted and stored data. Another trial to load unstructured extracted data into a database and transform it to semi-structured or structured format by storing necessary tweet details such as tweet identity and message, user name, time, and sentiment score to enhance the reports generation process was done in [14] who developed a system for opinion analysis using data pulled from twitter posts with a connection to Alchemy API by using REST call method.

Working with twitter is easier than working with reviews as the tweets include text with limitation to 140 characters and this makes it easier to extract valuable information. Researchers have begun studying content obtained from microblogging services such as Twitter to address a variety of technological, social and commercial research questions [1]. A very good brief knowledge about twitter sentiment analysis can be found in [16], [17], [19], and [20] that discussed sentiment analysis in various aspects including different levels, approaches, methodologies, applications, and explicit features extracted from text with comparative analysis of existing techniques for opinion mining like machine learning and lexicon-based approaches, together with evaluation metrics. An easy way to do data mining is using ready-existing tool to extract useful information to classify sentiments of tweets collected from Twitter with getting benefits from the results in judging sentiment of new tweets. In this context, researchers proposed an approach that used Weka data mining tool or software with a positive and negative word set to be compared to another set of words extracted from twitter taking into consideration the emoticons as features [15]. Researchers in [24] also proposed a way to determine public opinions from twitter data with concentration on finding the sentiments in specific locations to allow companies to focus on areas where sentiment is low and maintaining advertisements in areas of high popularity. They

obtained features from specific tweets by including the feature name with the product name in the crawler research target and this limits the number of features without finding or extracting new features that are not known before.

When talking about sentiment analysis, [25] focused on classifying polarity of a set of opinioned tweets about a specific product into either negative, neutral, and positive tweets using machine learning algorithms. Although most of researchers did work on applying sentiment analysis on data extracted from Twitter, there were others working with analysing reviews from web forums. In 2013, researchers proposed methods to extract valuable sentiment data from opinion posts that are considered to be brief text fragments expressing sentiments about specific business objects with pointing out the advantages and disadvantages regarding to different features of products [18]. Fig 3 shows an example of the extraction of useful insights from user reviews.

In 2017, researchers used VADER sentiment analysis tool for unsupervised and online sentiment analysis of product reviews. They stated that Vader had performed the best among the other unsupervised methods. On tweet datasets Vader had accuracies of 84.4 and 99% [6]. According to that, VADER had been used in our work as a sentiment analysis tool but with different application on extracted social data came from twitter instead of applying on users' reviews.

Fig. 3. Opinion data extracted from an example opinion post

In 2010, researchers proposed a method for an automatic collection of a corpus used in training sentiment classifier and determining positive, neutral, and negative sentiments of documents based on the multinational Naïve Bayes classifier that uses N-gram and POS-tags as features [7]. Using N-gram as features for the classification process is not always sufficient and not a condition to ensure high accuracy. In [13], researchers proposed an approach for automatically classifying the sentiment of twitter messages toward product or brand using emoticons mainly and to increase the accuracy, they used bigrams (two-word combination) as features to include the negation, if exist, in the opinion phrase but using them as classification features did not give any good improvement in results because the feature space is very sparse and there are other researchers who are not satisfied also from using bi-grams [13]. Our work discussed using N-grams in extracting phrases from tweets with different values for N and identified the problems of applying that in the analysis process.

Some researchers proposed a supervised sentiment classification framework that used data from twitter and use different features types to sentiment classification like punctuation, checking distribution of words frequencies, different n-gram models and patterns. Other researchers developed tools for automatic sentiment analysis for unstructured data with considering both subjective and objective sentences (opinionated and non-opinionated) and then classification for positive, neutral and negative sentiments. As sentence level sentiment analysis, [13] also introduced an approach for automatically classifying the sentiment of twitter messages toward a specific product/brand using emoticons with improved text pre-processing process to achieve high accuracy although there is no handling of contradicting emoticons. Our work is different from theirs as we are not depending on emotions to do the sentiment analysis but we concentrated on finding opinion phrases in the tweet text.

Some researchers used hashtags in doing sentiment analysis by studying the hashtag level of sentiment analysis and generate overall sentiment of tweets using two stages SVM classifier. Besides using machine learning techniques like researchers in [19] as they used also symbolic techniques and identified the idea of feature vector that includes specific features of twitter like hashtags and emoticons related to specific features. This feature vector is composed from eight relevant features: POS tag, special key word, presence of negation, emotion, number of positive word, number of negative words, number of positive hashtags and number of negative tags. All of this work discussed was done based on the sentence level sentiment analysis even generally or for specific target topic without any sentence segmentation or identification of specific words inside the text. Our concentration is in the area of entity level sentiment analysis (feature based) discussing different ways to do that and previous work done in that area whether working on reviews or tweets.

A leading research done in that area was in 2004 by Hu and Liu as they summarized all the customer reviews of a product with concentration on specific features of the products that customers have opinions on and identifying the polarity of these opinions as positive or negative. They concentrated mainly on finding frequent and infrequent features according to the appearing and repeating in the reviews [21].

Researchers in [27] used POS tag to spot features and opinions in customer reviews of mobile phones, while in [28]; researchers used this extraction method to extract opinion words that described the features of a product from review texts. They used the pattern knowledge supported linguistic rules to extract features that are nouns or noun phrases and identified domain product features that are talked about by customers by using the manually tagged training corpus for domain features. POS extraction extracts all of the words in a sentence containing opinion words and unwanted words too. Because of that, these is a need to use another extraction way which is done by using the dependency parser is used for extracting noun phrases which form the candidate aspects. In [22], researchers proposed a novel way to recognize (product features – opinion) pairs by using a probabilistic model with syntactic information based on dependency relationships.

Researchers in [30] used some rules based on observations and some rules from previous work and list the most useful

dependency relations from previous work and also theirs. The limitation here is that with comparative sentences as it is not easy to map the right relations between opinions and product aspects and this approach can be improved by applying more rules and finding more useful dependencies along with expanding the opinion lexicon. In [31], researchers used the rule-based method to extract opinion words on document and sentence levels and the polarity of words is obtained by referring to the sentiment lexicon. Because of the limitations of both POS extraction and rule-based extraction methods, researchers in [32] integrated both methods to improve opinion words extractions. They stated that the process of identifying opinion of a particular feature in a sentence is quite tedious and troublesome. To conclude, rule-based extraction methods work well in grammatically correct sentences. The disadvantage of this method is that it works poorly on online text where rules of linguistics are not followed. This is because sentences can sometimes be written while completely disregarding rules of grammar.

As an assumption for a new idea and instead of dealing with tweets separately in the analysis process, [26] proposed method that considered the whole tweets conversations not only individual tweets as a reply tree and employs links to effectively extract product features involved in the messages by using POS tagging and filter features based on appearing at least three times in the messages with frequency > 0.02.

Another way of thinking is by using phrase dependency parsing to extract relations between product features phrases and expressions of opinions, as done in [29], as authors focus on phrases and finding the relations between them rather than on the single words inside each phrase.

There are other ways to complete the extraction process. One of them is used in [33] that used Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) to jointly extract object features and positive and negative opinions from review sentences. Researchers in [34] detected the features in a review sentence using POS tag and identified the opinion words and the polarity of the words using a lexicon. They used distance method to compute the sentiment score for features. [35] used the same method to determine the features polarity of tourism products.

Researchers in [22] adopted linguistic filtering pattern to extract opinion phrases based on POS tags for words and for each noun phrase in every dependency and generated potential syntactic information of noun phrase – adjective word pair. Although this approach takes advantages of the dependency relationship and machine learning, there are still a lot of errors caused by complex sentences. Researchers in [23] also compared between two algorithms which are: association rule mining (Apriori algorithm) and sequential pattern mining (Generalized Sequential Pattern (GSP)) to find frequent features and opinions by finding the best extracted meaningful rules or patterns that helps in ensuring from product features. In [55], researchers identified the most characteristic features of a product first by using association rule mining and they continued by developing supervised machine learning algorithm based on polarity classifier that determines the sentiment of the review sentence with respect to the prominent features. They considered the most frequent POS tag within the context of previous three and next three tokens as the features of the classification model and this consideration is not sufficient when dealing with complex sentences. Researchers in [21] used Apriori algorithm to find all frequent

itemsets from a set of transactions that satisfy a user-specified minimum support and generate rules from the discovered frequent itemsets with three words or fewer.

Authors of [38] developed a system that automatically integrates unstructured data into RDBMS by using text analytic approach to extract relevant information from academic journals to build a structured database which can be analysed to support decision making. With a reference to social media, [37] proposed a business intelligence architecture called Online Social Networks Business Intelligence Architecture (OSNBIA) to achieve the integration by extracting data from twitter and applies social network and sentiment analysis to generate a data warehouse enabling new possibilities of OSN data manipulation through business intelligence technologies like QlikView providing greater flexibility for scenario analysis. Researchers in [36] presented an approach to integrate sentiment data extracted from web feeds into the corporate warehouse. The important problem has been the unification of features that refer to the same meaning to treat as synonymous groups. Fig 4 shows their architecture of the proposed integration and sources of corporate and opinion data.

Fig. 4. Architecture of the proposed integration and sources of corporate and opinion data.

IV. SOCIAL – CORPORATE DATA JOINING FRAMEWORK

Given a dataset of texts containing opinions about a specific product and extracted from social media platform based on the name of that product as the target, there is a need to find a way to deal with the large unstructured noisy text to get some valuable information. There is a need to classify the semantic orientation of an entity towards a given feature term in the text aiming at recognizing the characteristics of a product combined with the most nearby opinion phrase describing that feature and this is done in three main steps:

1. Extraction of product entities (features).
2. Identification of opinion words which are associated with the entities.
3. Determination of these opinions' semantic orientation is positive and negative.

the objective of opinion mining on texts is to extract useful opinions about product features with polarity definition of each feature taking into consideration the opinion phrases that have polarity and the existence of the negation in this opinion phrase and represent them in a format that is easy to digest with summarization and calculation of statistical information needed to benefit from that data. Fig 5 shows the flow of the

processes till discovering the new valuable output that is considered to help decision makers to improve the decision making process.

Fig. 5. Flow of proposed framework processes

The proposed architecture consisted of mainly four layers. They started by doing some pre-processing steps on the extracted texts from social media to be able to extract the features from each text sequentially using different techniques. After that, the opinion words that are related to each feature are with the identification of the semantic orientation of each opinion in positive or negative polarity. Finally, the proposed approach had been tested on a sample test data containing manually-updated English opined texts and then some statistical measurements and classification analysis are being resulted and visualized. Before going deeply in the details of the proposed approach steps, Fig 6 summarized these steps in an architectural way. The framework worked on the twitter dataset using Python with different libraries and functions for each process.

Fig. 6. Social – Corporate Data Joining Framework

To get all of the benefits from the resulted data, we integrated the founded results after storing them in a structured data format with the corporate structured database to get more compound reports including information that cannot be found from each database separately. The next subsections discussed all of the layers of the proposed approach in detail.

As a start, the input dataset consisted of 500 opinion tweet texts extracted from Twitter platform in CSV format containing opinions on a camera as a product. The format of the CSV file is as a table consisting of two attributes: TweetId which is the tweet text identification number and TweetText which is the opinion tweet text. An example of a raw extracted tweet text is shown in fig 7.

```

Raw tweet
RT. @mention I love my camera because it took a very good pictures but when the screen
stops working, you're out of luck! https://www.earthdatascience.org/courses/earth-
analytics-python/using-apis-natural-language-processing-twitter/analyze-tweet-sentiments-
in-python/
    
```

Fig. 7. Sample raw tweet text

It is assumed that each product will be extracted separately from other products and in this work, each CSV file is containing extracted tweets related to only one product. This dataset is managed manually in this work to fit the objective of the work and to cover all the cases need to be discussed.

A. Text Pre-processing Layer

Different processes applied before extracting product features from the opinion input text with their representative opinion phrases. Generally, users are much more likely to have grammatical spelling errors when writing posts on different social media platforms. As a result, regular expression matching of common errors and substituting with standard language is necessary. Also there is a need to remove acronyms or replacing them with their expanded form, handling sequences of repeated characters, and ignoring all non-ASCII characters. The reason is that the clearer the data, the more suitable they are for mining and feature extraction which leads to the improved accuracy of the results. This is done using NLTK module's functions in python that provides functionality for symbolic and statistical natural language processing. All of this had been handled and discussed in the following steps included in the first sub-process which is the text cleaning process.

1. Remove all emoticons as they are not included in this work concentration and handling.
2. Non- informative phrases like, in Twitter, (@username), URL links, "RT" keyword indicating retweet and hashtags were stripped from the tweets.
3. Remove Acronyms or replaced with their expanded form.
4. Remove all non-informative stop words.
5. All digits and unnecessary punctuation were removed.
6. Handle sequence of repeated characters.
7. Ignore all non-ASCII characters.
8. Remove names of the targeted brand or product.
9. All texts are converted to lowercase.

Then, there is an ability to develop very specialized tag sets to accommodate specific research needs. After that, each tagged token is represented using a tuple consisting of the token and the tag. We constructed a list of tagged tokens for each cleaned tweet text in a form of tuple. Table 1 present the output of each step in the text cleaning process. The output of this sub-process is a list of cleaned opinion sentences.

For each tweet after pre-processing, it is divided into segments or parts using different NLTK modules. Then POS

tagging included in NLTK module is applied to find the lexical category for each word in each segment (noun, verb, preposition, etc.). There are many reasons why splitting a document or a sentence can be useful for text analysis as explained in previous chapter. One of the main reasons is because they are smaller and more coherent than the whole sentence. The task of sentence segmentation aims to split the sentence into a sequence of exclusive parts, each of which is a basic computational unit of the sentence. In this work, we tried applying three different modules for doing text segmentation of each sentence. Fig 8 shows the steps of the first module which uses Tokenization and POS tagging. Fig 9 shows the steps of the second module which uses N-gram Modelling and POS tagging. Fig 10 shows the steps of the third module which uses Chunking or Shallow Parsing and POS tagging.

```

Input: A sentence contains a cleaned tweet text
Output: A list of the sentence segments with their POS tags

List of tokens = NLTK Word Tokenization (sentence)
For token in List of tokens
    Find POS tag (token)
    Save (token , POS tag) in list
List of generated tuples (token, POS tag)
    
```

Fig. 8. Tokenization Extraction Module

```

Input: A sentence contains a cleaned tweet text
Output: A list of the sentence segments with their POS tags

#Define the value of n
    Set value of n
#Divide the input string into parts, each contains n words or tokens
    generate_ngrams(input string, value of n)
#Generate list of ngrams
    list(ngrams(tokens, value of n))
    
```

Fig. 9. N-gram Extraction Module

```

Input: A sentence contains a cleaned tweet text
Output: A list of the sentence segments with their POS tags

#split the sentence into small word tokens
    Tokenize (input string)
#find the POS tag for each token
    POS Tagging (tokens)
#Define a rule grammar pattern
    Set grammar pattern
    Use RegexpParser (grammar pattern)
#apply the pattern on the sentence tokens to get chunks
    Parse (sentence) based on the grammar pattern
#show the result as a tree
    Draw resulted chunks
    
```

Fig. 10. Chunking Extraction Module

TABLE 1

TEXT CLEANING STEPS AND OUTPUTS

Text Cleaning Steps	Tweet Text
Raw Tweet Text	RT @mention I love my camera coz it took a very good woooooo Pictures but when the screen stops working, you're out of luck! ☹ ☹ #Waaaaa http://www.earthdatascience.org/courses/earth-analytics-python/
Remove URLs	RT @mention I love my camera coz it took a very good woooooo Pictures but when the screen stops working, you're out of luck! ☹ ☹ #Waaaaa
Remove retweets, hashtags, and mentions	I love my camera coz it took a very good woooooo Pictures but when the screen stops working, you're out of luck! ☹ ☹
Remove unnecessary punctuation	I love my camera coz it took a very good woooooo Pictures but when the screen stops working you're out of luck ☹ ☹
Remove emoticons	I love my camera coz it took a very good woooooo Pictures but when the screen stops working you're out of luck
Remove repeated characters and spell correction	I love my camera coz it took a very good wow Pictures but when the screen stops working you're out of luck
Convert to lower case	i love my camera coz it took a very good wow pictures but when the screen stops working you're out of luck
Stemming and Lemmatization	i love my camera because it take a very good pictures but when the screen stop work you are out of luck

B. Extraction Process Layer

The extraction of the features and opinions are implemented in three methods with a comparison between them to state the problems and challenges in each method. The First method is done by applying POS extraction. After applying the tokenization process, each opinion text has been divided into separate tokens. Having the text as a list of tokens, it was used as the input for the POS tagging process to define the POS for each word or token. An algorithm was generated to check sequentially every single word in the whole sentence and check if its POS tag is NOUN or not with concatenation of the successive nouns to be one single noun phrase representing the product feature. Then, the algorithm went through every word before or after this noun phrase to check the possessive and successive words before or after the noun phrase to know if their POS tag is ADJ (adjective) or not. If so, a tuple containing the extracted noun phrase with the extracted opinion word which is the adjective before or

after the related and described feature had been generated. The new generated list containing tuples or pairs of feature phrase and opinion phrase was entered on the sentiment analysis algorithm that analysed the opinion phrase, decide its polarity without taking into consideration the existence of the negation in the opinion phrase as positive, neutral, or negative, and find the sentiment that is related to each feature after calculating the sentiment score for each extracted opinion phrase. Fig 11 shows the flowchart of the processes of that algorithm.

Fig. 11. POS Extraction Process

This method has many shortcomings, problems and limitations. First, we need to go through all of the text to extract the features and the opinions every time for each tweet separately. This may take long execution time because of the sequential search for what is needed to be extracted. Second, we can find nouns or successive nouns that are not necessary to be a feature name and this can be handled or removed after that in the filtration process where we find the frequency for each extracted feature and try to discover the features with frequency less than specific assumed threshold. Third, this technique depends on using adjectives only to find the sentiment for each extracted features with neglecting the features with no founded adjectives directly before or after them to decide the polarity and this will cause losing information from neglected features that may be important for the organization to know because of the nature of the tweet text, there is a need to have more flexible technique to deal with this unstructured and non-grammatical text to be able to find other words that can be used to decide the polarity of these words and attach to the related feature. Fig 12 shows an example that shows the application of this module on the input sentence.

Input Sentence: "I love my camera because it took a very good pictures but When the screen stops working, you are out of luck"
List of Tokens: ['i', 'love', 'my', 'camera', 'because', 'it', 'took', 'a', 'very', 'good', 'pictures', 'but', 'when', 'the', 'screen', 'stops', 'working', 'you', 'are', 'out', 'of', 'luck']
After removing stop words: ['love', 'camera', 'took', 'good', 'pictures', 'screen', 'stops', 'working', 'luck']
POS Tagging: [('love', 'NN'), ('camera', 'NN'), ('took', 'VBD'), ('good', 'JJ'), ('pictures', 'NNS'), ('screen', 'JJ'), ('stops', 'NNS'), ('working', 'VBG'), ('luck', 'NN')]

Fig. 12. Tokenization Extraction Example

The second method is the same as the previous method with an extra step inside the flow of processes by applying the N-gram modelling. N-gram is the simplest model between different statistical language models that assign probabilities to the consecutive sequences of N words. N-gram models are considered to be widely used in probability, communication theory, computational linguistics in NLP, computational biology and data compression. The benefits of using N-gram models are the simplicity and scalability. They are used more in word prediction and in calculating sentence probability.

Using N-gram to segments the text, there are many extracted features that were extracted without including the adjectives with them in the bigram or trigram. In [23], researches hinted the use of N-grams in the segmentation process. Fig 13 shows an example that shows the application of this algorithm on the input sentence assuming that N = 2.

Input Sentence: "Although the battery life is not the best, the phone is pretty amazing"
After removing stop words: ['although', 'battery', 'life', 'best', 'phone', 'pretty', 'amazing']
POS Tagging: [('although', 'IN'), ('battery', 'NN'), ('life', 'NN'), ('best', 'RBS'), ('phone', 'NN'), ('pretty', 'RB'), ('amazing', 'JJ')]
List of Bigrams: [(although battery), (battery life), (life best), (best phone), (phone pretty), (pretty amazing)]

Fig. 13. N-gram Extraction Example when N = 2

After searching for a more suitable method to be able to extract product features with their descriptive opinion phrase with handling the shortcomings from previous two methods, a new extraction method called syntactic chunking. Syntactic chunking is also called shallow parsing. Similar to POS tags, there are a standard set of chunk tags like noun phrases (NP), verb phrases (VP), etc. Noun phrase chunking is used to search for chunks corresponding to an individual noun phrase by defining the chunk grammar using specific grammar pattern or identifying rules. These rules can be grouped into single regular expression rule to group nouns with the describing expression that is in relation to them as opinion phrases. There is a need to control defined pattern and grammar rules to include any number of descriptive words before or after the feature that can be also any number of nouns.

In order to create an NP-chunker, a chunk grammar is being defined which is consisting of rules that indicate how sentences should be chunked. In this case, we defined a set of simple grammar with multiple regular expression rules. For example, one rule says that an NP chunk should be formed whenever the chunker finds an optional determiner (DT) followed by any number of adjectives (JJ) and then a noun (NN). Using this grammar pattern, a chunk parser, and test it on our example sentence. The result is a tree, which we can either print, or display graphically. This method can be used directly to extract the pattern that we already searched for. A grammar pattern that handles most of the needed cases has been defined when searching for nouns or successive nouns in the sentence and then find a descriptive phrase or after the extracted noun phrase. The result is a tree containing the noun chunks and each one is consisted of the noun phrase and the descriptive phrase (opinion phrase) which may contain any or all of the verbs, adverbs, or adjectives with taking the negation into consideration as it affects the sentiment of the opinion phrase.

spaCy library is being used as it is an open source library for advanced NLP in python. It is not a platform or API, not a chat bot engine and not research software. spaCy dependency parsing by assigning syntactic dependency labels, describing the relations between individual tokens based on their texts and linguistic annotations, similar to regular expressions. We used the Regexparser to parse the pre-defined grammar. We defined a grammar pattern that handles most of the cases when searching for nouns or successive nouns in the sentence and then find a descriptive phrase or after the extracted noun

phrase. Fig 14 shows an example that shows the application of this module on the input sentence

Input Sentence: "the lens is visible in the viewfinder when the lens is set to the wide angle , till i use the lcd most of the time."			
Noun Chunks: (S (NP the/DET lens/NOUN is/VERB visible/ADJ) (NP in/ADP the/DET viewfinder/NOUN when/ADV) (NP the/DET lens/NOUN is/VERB set/VERB to/PRT) (NP the/DET wide/ADJ angle/NOUN till/NOUN use/ADP) (NP the/DET lcd/NOUN most/ADJ) (NP of/ADP the/DET time/NOUN))			
Resulted Output:			
	Tweet ID	Feature	Opinion
	0	1	lens the is visible
	1	1	viewfinder in the when
	2	1	lens the is set to
	3	1	angle till the wide use
	4	1	lcd the most

Fig. 14. Chunking Extraction Example

C. Sentiment Analysis Layer

After filtering the list of extracted features and keep only the representative features that affect the production and marketing processes and that are important to be known from the decision makers, there is a need to define the polarity definition for each opinion phrase extracted with each related feature. There are a lot of algorithms that can be applied to define the polarity of these phrases as positive, neutral, or negative and put a score for each identified polarity to classify the results based on sentiment analysis process. The output of this layer is a list of filtered features, each with a number of negative opinions and number of positive opinions about that feature. We used VADER sentiment library in Python.

VADER not only tells about the positivity and negativity scores but also tells about how positive or negative a sentiment is. VADER analyzes the text by checking to see if any of the words in the text are present in the lexicon and produced four sentiment metrics from word ratings. They are the positive, neutral, negative, and the compound score which is the sum of all of the lexicon ratings which have standardized to range between -1 and 1. The positive sentiment has compound score ≥ 0.05 , negative sentiment has compound score ≤ -0.05 , and the neutral sentiment with compound score > -0.05 and < 0.05 . After finalizing the sentiment analysis process, there is a need to group and classify the features according to the extracted opinion sentiment related to each feature. The output of this layer is a table that contains the following attributes: feature Id, feature name, positive tweets, and negative tweets.

D. Integration and Visualization Layer

The generated list from the previous layer put the unstructured data extracted from social media in a structured and representative format by storing them in a structured database. The new designed database contains a table with attributes: FeatureId that represent identification number of each extracted feature, number of negative opinions, and number of positive opinions. This generated database then joined with the corporate traditional database by generating the relations between the tables depending on the product identification number. A lot of queries and reports have been generated using this join between these databases. Fig 15 shows a schema for representing the join between these databases.

Fig. 15. Integrated Database Model

V. EVALUATION

The evaluation of the proposed framework is applied actually of the extraction layer which implemented three different methods and after some calculations we are able to compare between these methods according to their accuracy. The proposed framework had been applied on a sample dataset containing 500 tweets attached with their extracted features for each tweet and sentiment analysis of each related opinion. Accuracy is the proximity of measurement results to the true value as it is the proportion of the true results (both true positives and true negatives) among the total number of cases examined.

The accuracy had been calculated for the three methods of extraction. Tokenization and POS extraction method gives accuracy of 69% and N-gram modelling and POS tagging method gives accuracy of 63%. About the chunking method, the accuracy was 77%. These results are summarized and charted in Fig 16.

Fig. 16. Comparing Accuracy of the three methods

About precision, it represents how many selected items are relevant. It represents the number of the true positives divided by the total number of elements labelled as belonging to the positive class. In measurement of a set, accuracy refers to closeness of the measurements to a specific value while precision refers to the closeness of the measurements to each other. Recall is representing how many relevant items are selected. It is the fraction of the total amount of relevant instances that were actually retrieved. Both precision and

recall are based on an understanding and measure of relevance. Precision also can be seen as a measure of exactness or quality whereas recall is a measure of completeness or quantity. The exact relationship between sensitivity and specify to precision depends on the percentage of positive cases in the population. These calculations have been applied on the algorithm using the different three methods. Table 2 shows the results of the precision and recall for the three methods. Recall value is higher than the precision value which proves that the majority of correct features were correctly recognized by the system. Precision value is lower than recall value indicates that certain identified features are not correct.

TABLE 2
PRECISION AND RECALL CALCULATIONS SUMMARIZATION

Method	Precision	Recall
Method 1	0.686275	0.694444
Method 2	0.660517	0.653285
Method 3	0.77381	0.506494

VI. DISCUSSION

By applying the use of NLTK Tokenization and POS Tagging, Noun Chunking and Dependency Parsing, and N-Gram Modelling, we worked on dataset of tweets after text pre-processing, finding frequent features and doing sentiment analysis. Doing text segmentation in extracting features from text is better than searching for nouns and adjectives in the whole text. Using Noun Chunking is the best between the three methodologies as we can specify exactly the grammatical pattern that we need to get the features and opinion words from and this makes the process easier and restricted. After that, we classified the tweets according to the output results to get the most feature with positive opinions, the most feature with negative opinions and relate them to the different locations that tweets came from, the effect of that on the product sales and make decision makers try to enhance these product features as a type of production improvement. Fig 17 represents the number of positive and negative tweets for each extracted feature based on applying the chunking extraction method in the proposed framework for a sample output features. Sample output with some counting results based on applying the third method in the proposed framework implementation are stated in table 3.

TABLE 3
EXTRACTED FEATURES WITH REPRESENTATIVE NUMBER OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE TWEETS

Extracted Features	Number of Positive Tweets	Number of Negative Tweets
Battery	51	45
Lens	30	32
Viewfinder	49	55
Flash	20	10
Photo quality	23	16
Video quality	12	9
Zoom	21	33
Camera resolution	32	29
Lens cap	14	19

Fig. 17. Counting Results Visualization

By referring to fig 18, we can discover that battery feature has the most negative comments in Canada although it is generally not the worst feature. China and Australia have the most negative comments about the viewfinder which is generally detected as the worst feature.

Fig. 18. Number of negative tweets in different locations

The integrated database is considered to be the only possible mean for answering queries involving both data sources. Queries can be represented and visualized using different types of reports, dashboards and charts. Table 4 presents a sample of such queries. Using the SCDJF framework enables organizations to perform analysis tasks on the integrated social and corporate data. They can generate insights that can help in decision making process and hence, enabling customers' engagement, listening to the voice of the market and having a full view for the market.

TABLE 4
LIST OF QUERIES ON THE INTEGRATED DATA MODEL

Query Number	Query Description
Q1	Comparison between the sales and the number of positive and negative opinion in a specific period of time in several locations.
Q2	Comparison between countries to identify best country, the one that has the maximum number of positive opinions with the sales of the same country.
Q3	Country Ranking according to a comparison between numbers of positive opinions for each country with respect to the amount of sold products.
Q4	Country Ranking according to a comparison between numbers of negative opinions for each country with respect to the amount of sold products.
Q5	Comparison between the sales and the number of positive and negative opinions of specific features related to specific product
Q6	Finding best product feature with respect to the sales in a specific period of time in several locations
Q7	Finding worst product feature with respect to the sales in a specific period of time in several locations

The first three queries in previous table represent an overall opinion with respect to the whole product. The following figures show a representation for evaluating these queries on three different types of products according to a dataset that contains customers' opinions with their sentiment analysis and polarity identification for each opinion with respect to specific product features. Fig 19 presents a key performance indicator that compare the sales values of the product Canon-G3 as an example with the sales goal defined in data warehouse in different locations which showing the influence of positive and negative opinions that clarify the results.

Fig. 19. Number of negative tweets in different locations

The decision maker can drill down through the results until the opinions text level to obtain the reason for any performance. Three locations, Canada, Philippines and Japan were represented an example for the performance of product Canon-G3 in the same figure. The three locations were

performing under the goal, within the goal, and better than the sales KPI respectively. There is a direct correlation between the sale and customer satisfaction represented by the positive and negative values compared with sales values in each of the three countries. Customer Satisfaction is calculated for each product separately using this equation: $[(X/Y)*Z]$ where X is the number of positive opinions in a specific country, Y is the number of negative opinions in a specific country and Z is the amount of sold products in a specific country. The results of the query are shown in Fig 20. The decision maker can drill down through the results until the opinions text level to obtain the reason for any performance. There is a direct correlation between the sales and customer satisfaction represented by positive and negative values for features compared with sales values for each the products.

Fig. 20. Country Ranking according to positive and negative opinions of different sold products

VII. CONCLUSION

We studied doing sentiment analysis on the feature level after extracting every product feature from each tweet text which may contain more than one feature with the related opinion word as adjectives. Sentiment Analysis was applied to define the polarity of opinions attached with each feature separately which resulted in that each one tweet may contain more than one sentiment and they may be contradicting with each other, so, working with feature level instead of the sentence level as a whole is better in this case. The results showed the differences between using different methodologies in text pre-processing and feature extraction and how this will affect the decision making and production enhancement strategies.

We proposed a social business intelligence framework called Social – Corporate Data Joining Framework (SCDJF) that indicates to join between social media and corporate database. We demonstrated the applicability of our framework using a case study for a corporate data and social media data that were integrated using the proposed framework. Using the resulted integrated data, we were able to perform queries that give the decision makers more insights into their corporate.

In our future work, we plan to monitor customers' opinions and integrate them with corporate database automatically and periodically. We believe that monitoring will be particularly useful to product manufacturers because they want to know

any new positive or negative opinions about their products whenever they are available. More specifically, with respect to the extraction of product features, further refinement techniques should be developed in order to filter out possible features that are taken for valid when they are not. One promising direction is to enable contents analysis of opinions by building corresponding keyword indices, enabling language detection and translation as well as spam filtering. In terms of performance, our goal is to provide a near real-time analysis by optimizing the loading of the new data. There is a need to take into consideration the existence of the negation words before the opinion words which will change the polarity of the extracted opinion word to be the opposite of it and accordingly, this will change the output results. There is a need also to decide on the polarity of verbs inside the sentence in case of adjectives are not enough to decide the polarity or may be not found. Consideration also needs to be taken on the average polysemy of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs according to WordNet. Also there is a need to improve the proposed framework techniques especially in the extraction process layer to be able to extract implicit features that are not stated directly and obviously in the opinion text. Another case study also can be found to crawl and pull data from different social media platforms and how this can be managed and joined to convert the different data formats to a specific data format that will be easier to be integrated with the corporate database.

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